

seedling, and covered with a fine fiber glass-mesh cage. Damage was scored on the 0-9 scale of the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)* when TN1 was killed.

Population growth was studied by infesting 30-d-old potted test plants with five pairs of GLH adults. The plants were covered with mylar film cages and arranged in a randomized complete block design, replicated five times. Nymphs

Pest resistance— other pests

New ultra-resistant rice lines

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During 1990-93, we tested and selected 29 F₂ populations and their progenies for ultra (*Ditylenchus angustus*) resistance. One hundred twenty-four selected lines of F₃ populations were further evaluated in 1993. Seeds of each of these entries were sown in pots and inoculated with 100 nematodes/plant at 15 d. Entries were scored 6 wk after inoculation based on leaf symptoms of susceptibility (Fig. 1a) and resistance (Fig. 1b-d).

Ten seedlings from each of the entries with resistance symptoms were transplanted for field evaluation from booting to flowering stages. A few seedlings with primary infestations and resistance symptoms were marked with

and adults on each plant were counted 30 d after infestation.

Thirteen varieties, ASD7, Tendeng, Rhissa, Sefa, Badal, Chota Digha, Chiknal, Ptb8, ASD8, Tapl796, Moddai Karuppan, Choron Bawla, and Laki 659, were rated as resistant in the seedbox screening test (see table). Pankhari 203 with *Glh 1* gene, and Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 with a dominant gene, were rated as susceptible. Population

increase was significantly higher on TN1, Pankhari 203, Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 than that on the resistant varieties.

Among the GLH resistance genes identified at IRRI, *Glh 1* and a dominant gene in Hashikalmi, Ghaiya, and ARC10313 do not confer resistance to GLH populations in Tamil Nadu while varieties with *Glh 2*, *Glh 3*, *glh 4*, *Glh 5*, *Glh 6*, *Glh 7*, *Glh 1* + *Glh 2*, and *Glh 3* + *Glh 5* do confer resistance. ■

Rice entries with ultra resistance. BRRI, Bangladesh.

Plant type	Entries		
Tall	IR63142-J6-B-1	IR63142-J8-B-2	IR63155-J9-B-1
	IR63174-J1-B-3	IR63188-J8-B-1	IR63188-J8-B-7
	IR63225-J2-B-1	IR63225-J2-B-4	IR63225-J2-B-6
	IR63645-J3-B-8		
Short	IR63174-J1-B-2-3	IR63174-J1-B-3-2	IR63174-J1-B-3-1
	IR63174-J1-B-4-3	IR63174-J1-B-6-3	IR63174-J2-B-4-2
	IR63174-J3-B-1-2		

red cellophane tape to record their survival. After establishment, five plants from each of these entries were dissected to count nematode populations. Rayada 16-06-1 was the resistant check and Habiganj Aman II, the susceptible check.

Sixty-four of the lines survived and flowered successfully. Ten deepwater rice lines (see table) had mild or no resistance symptoms. Seven other resistant entries (see table) were short-stemmed and may be used as resistance sources for rainfed lowland and irrigated rices. These entries had either Bazail 65 or Rayada 16-06 as a resistant parent.

Seedlings with primary infestations and resistance symptoms did not survive to maturity in all of the marked lines, but 91-96% of the secondary tillers that emerged from them survived and flowered successfully. In contrast, neither seedlings with primary infestations nor

secondary tillers of susceptible varieties survived. Nematode numbers were 0-101/plant in resistant entries and 141-3280 in the susceptible ones. Rayada 16-06-1, however, did not have any symptoms or nematodes in this experiment. ■

Integrated germplasm improvement

Twelve new rice varieties released for Orissa State, India

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The Orissa State Subcommittee recommended the release of 12 new rice varieties, developed by OUAT, for commercial cultivation in the state. Badami (OR164-5), Nilagiri (OR163-104), Khandagiri (OR811-2), and Ghanteswari (OR377-85-6) are adapted to rainfed and irrigated upland ecosystems; Birupa (OR253-2), Meher (OR526-2008-4), Samanta (OR487-30-3) and Bhanja (OR443-80-4), four midseason varieties, are recommended for irrigated

Symptoms of ultra disease on rice leaves. Susceptible: splash pattern chlorosis (a); resistant: discrete or rounded chlorotic lesion (b, d), elongated chlorotic lesion (c).